

Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution Markov Chain Method

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Abstract

Bayesian inverse problems governed by partial differential equations (PDEs) are often characterized by high-dimensional parameter spaces and computationally expensive forward models, making efficient posterior exploration challenging. Function-space Markov chain Monte Carlo (McMC) methods such as the preconditioned Crank–Nicolson (pCN) algorithm provide dimension-robust proposals by preserving the prior distribution, but their exploration efficiency may deteriorate in anisotropic or strongly likelihood-informed regimes. Population-based Differential Evolution (DE) proposals can improve global exploration by exploiting ensemble information, yet they typically sacrifice prior invariance and lack guarantees in function-space settings. In this work, we introduce the Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution (pCNDE) method, a new McMC proposal that integrates differential evolution directions into the pCN framework while preserving exact prior invariance and detailed balance. The resulting proposal retains the dimension-robust properties of pCN while automatically learning jump scale and orientation from an ensemble of chains, enabling efficient sampling with relatively small populations. We establish reversibility and posterior invariance of the resulting Markov chain and develop an asynchronous parallel implementation that reduces communication overhead in large-scale simulations. Numerical experiments on a nonlinear PDE-constrained Bayesian inverse problem in porous media demonstrate substantial efficiency gains over classical pCN, including higher acceptance rates and significantly fewer iterations to reach convergence. Performance is assessed using multichain stabilization diagnostics and wall-clock-normalized efficiency metrics. The

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proposed pCNDE method provides a scalable, theoretically grounded sampling strategy for high-dimensional Bayesian inverse problems governed by PDEs.

Keywords: Covariance function, Metropolis algorithm, Porous media, Bayesian inference

1. Introduction

Natural reservoirs show significant spatial variability in their hydraulic properties across multiple scales. Such variability significantly impacts fluid flow patterns within subsurface formations (Glimm et al., 1992, 1993; Furtado and Pereira, 2003; Borges et al., 2008). The diversity of scales, along with the lack of information, makes a deterministic description of these properties impractical. As a result, alternative methodologies are necessary that focus on a stochastic description of the subsurface (Dagan, 1989; Gelhar, 1993). According to Efendiev et al. (2006), the uncertainty in the characterization of reservoir parameters significantly contributes to the uncertainty in forecasting reservoir performance through computational simulations. In other words, the accuracy of computational models depends on the quality of the description of the formation properties.

Over the last decade, the significant increase in the acquisition of dynamic flow data (although in sparse locations) associated with the availability and use of high-performance computing has encouraged the use of Bayesian methods to characterize and reduce the uncertainties inherent in stochastic reservoir modeling. Data, such as well tests, production/pressure history, tracer injection, laboratory tests, CT-scan images, etc., are direct measurements of the reservoir exploration process and provide valuable information about the behavior of flows (Douglas et al., 2004, 2006). However, integrating them directly into computational models using conventional geostatistical techniques is usually challenging because the relationships between data and rock properties are nonlinear.

Matching field dynamic data with reservoir simulation represents a stochastic inverse problem (Iglesias et al., 2013) and can be formalized through Bayesian analysis and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods (Glimm et al., 1993). Bayesian inference is convenient for quantifying the added value of information from multiple sources (data). At the same time, MCMC methods provide a computational framework for sampling from the *a posteriori* distribution (see Robert and Casella (2005); Liu (2008)). The Metropolis algorithm (Metropolis et al., 1953) and its variants are an important class of

McMC algorithms widely used in the Bayesian analysis of stochastic inverse problems for their power and general applicability. In 2000, Computing in Science & Engineering, a joint publication of the IEEE Computer Society and the American Institute of Physics, placed the Metropolis Algorithm on the list of the ten algorithms with the most significant impact on the development of science and engineering practice in the 20th century (*Top Ten Algorithms of the Century* (Madey et al., 2005)). Despite its high computational cost, which, in some cases, can be prohibitive, McMC methods are regarded as the gold standard technique for Bayesian inference (Nemeth and Fearnhead, 2021) and have been widely used to solve stochastic inverse problems in porous media flow areas (Efendiev et al., 2005, 2006; Ma et al., 2008; Das et al., 2010; Mondal et al., 2010; Ginting et al., 2011, 2012; Akbarabadi et al., 2015, 2017; Ali et al., 2021).

The most significant difficulty in using McMC methods for flow problems in porous media is the high stochastic dimension of the parameter space (random fields), which leads to low acceptance rates. Thus, McMC simulations typically require thousands of iterations before they converge to the target distribution. Several procedures have been adopted to speed up the convergence and reduce the computational cost associated with the McMC methods: Adaptive Metropolis (Haario et al., 2001); Delayed Rejection (Tierney, 1994; Tierney and Mira, 1999); Delayed Rejection Adaptive Metropolis algorithm (Haario et al., 2006); Single Component Adaptive Metropolis (Haario et al., 2005); Differential Evolution Markov Chain (Vrugt et al., 2003; ter Braak, 2006); Differential Evolution Adaptive Metropolis (Vrugt et al., 2008), Domain Decomposition (Xu et al., 2024); Multiscale Bayesian Inference Method using a Multiscale Deep Generative Model (MDGM) (Xia and Zabarar, 2022); Multiscale sampling (Ali et al., 2024), among others.

Most of the time spent during subsurface characterization using McMC methods is spent running fine-scale simulations. To overcome this difficulty, the multi-stage McMC method (or preconditioned McMC), which uses up-scaled models to screen proposals, has been proposed (Christen and Fox, 2005; Efendiev et al., 2006). Therefore, inexpensive coarse-scale models are used to reduce the computational cost of fine-scale models and increase the sampling acceptance rate. If the proposal passes the coarse-scale model test, a fine-scale simulation will be performed in the second step to make a decision (accept or reject). Conversely, the proposal is rejected in the coarse-scale test, and no fine-mesh simulation is conducted.

Another common procedure to increase the acceptance rate of Markov Chain Monte Carlo (McMC) methods is to reduce the dimensionality of the stochastic fields. This approach is convenient in history matching, as it al-

lows the search to be conducted within a smaller parameter space. In this work, we focus on a specific method of this nature: the Karhunen-Loève expansion (Karhunen, 1946). This method relies on the eigen-decomposition of a covariance function. It has been widely utilized to represent high-dimensional permeability fields using a limited number of parameters in McMC studies. When the eigenvalues of a given covariance function decay rapidly, only a few terms need to be retained in the truncated expansion. In such instances, the Karhunen-Loève expansion significantly reduces the number of parameters required to generate correlated permeability fields. However, it is important to note that for some covariance functions, the eigenvalues may decay slowly. In these cases, more terms must be included in the truncated expansion, making the sampling of permeability from the distribution more computationally expensive for McMC methods. Another advantage of using the Karhunen-Loève expansion is that it represents correlated permeability fields through a set of uncorrelated random variables, thereby simplifying the search.

To ensure the efficiency of Markov Chain Monte Carlo (McMC) algorithms, one should choose the proposal distribution so that sampling from it is fast and easy. Furthermore, the shape and size of the proposal distribution are known to be crucial for the convergence of Markov chains (Haario et al., 1999; Gelman and Rubin, 1992; Gelman et al., 1996, 2013) and for efficiently exploring high-dimensional posterior distributions.

The Random-Walk Metropolis (RW) algorithm is the most straightforward approach, where each new candidate is obtained by adding a Gaussian perturbation to the current state. Although easy to implement, the RW scheme suffers from poor scalability, as its acceptance rate rapidly declines with increasing problem dimension (Roberts and Rosenthal, 2001).

To address the dimensional dependence of traditional proposals, the Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson (pCN) method (Cotter et al., 2013) was introduced. The pCN scheme modifies the random walk to ensure that the prior distribution remains invariant under the proposal. Consequently, the Metropolis acceptance probability depends solely on the likelihood function, improving performance for high-dimensional Bayesian inverse problems. However, selecting the appropriate jump parameter remains challenging, and adaptive variants of pCN, though effective, can be computationally demanding.

Another significant development is the Differential Evolution McMC (DE) algorithm proposed by ter Braak (2006), which integrates principles of genetic algorithms with McMC sampling. DE employs a population of parallel chains that exchange information through difference vectors between chain

states, automatically learning the scale and orientation of the target distribution. This approach enhances convergence and robustness for correlated or anisotropic posterior distributions, but it requires a relatively large number of chains to ensure proper exploration, thereby increasing computational cost.

Together, pCN and DE methodologies represent key milestones in the evolution of proposal mechanisms for MCMC methods. The present work builds upon the strengths of combining the dimension-robustness and prior invariance of pCN with the adaptive, population-based learning of DE to formulate the Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution (pCNDE) method, which aims to achieve efficient sampling even in high-dimensional Bayesian inverse problems. The pCN provides exact prior invariance and Hilbert-space well-posedness, whereas DE-like directions can enhance global exploration but typically do not preserve prior invariance. The central challenge addressed here is to incorporate differential directions into pCN while retaining detailed balance and the function-space structure.

The contributions of this work are: *(i)* a prior-invariant ensemble proposal (pCNDE) that augments pCN with differential directions while preserving exact prior invariance; *(ii)* a detailed-balance argument establishing posterior invariance under Metropolis–Hastings correction; *(iii)* a parallel/asynchronous implementation suitable for expensive PDE solves; and *(iv)* numerical evidence of improved stabilization of multichain diagnostics and wall-clock efficiency.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the Bayesian formulation of the inverse problem, including the stochastic flow model and the parameterization of the permeability field via the Karhunen–Loève expansion. Section 3 reviews the Markov chain Monte Carlo framework and summarizes the classical proposal mechanisms relevant to this work. Section 4 introduces the proposed Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution method (pCNDE) and discusses its theoretical properties and parallel implementation. Section 5 presents numerical experiments that assess the performance of the proposed method and compare it with the classical pCN approach.

2. Bayesian inverse problems

We are interested in solving inverse problems represented by:

$$\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} = \mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) + \boldsymbol{\psi}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ is the deterministic forward model, e.g., concerning a physical system. The function $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{R}^M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{Nd}$ maps the unknown parameter $\boldsymbol{\kappa} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ to the observable data $\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} \in \mathbb{R}^{Nd}$. $\boldsymbol{\psi} \in \mathbb{R}^{Nd}$ is the measurement noise. The parameter $\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$ is treated as a random field, where \mathbf{x} is a point in the domain $\mathcal{D} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ ($d = 1, 2, 3$) and ω is a random event in the probability space Ω . We assume that $\boldsymbol{\psi} \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$, where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the covariance function.

Given Eq. (1), we aim to sample the posterior distribution of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ based on its prior knowledge and the data \mathbf{D}^{obs} under the forward model \mathcal{F} . To accomplish this task, the data measurements are combined with the *a priori* distribution (or prior distribution, $P(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$) through Bayes' theorem to give

$$\pi(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = P(\boldsymbol{\kappa} | \mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}}) \propto P(\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} | \boldsymbol{\kappa}) P(\boldsymbol{\kappa}), \quad (2)$$

that is the target (*a posteriori*) distribution of the parameter $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. Before starting the process, the *a priori* distribution reflects our best knowledge of the parameters. Here, $\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = P(\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} | \boldsymbol{\kappa})$ is the likelihood function.

Next, we adapt the Bayesian inversion problem described previously to the single-phase flow in a heterogeneous porous medium addressed in this work.

2.1. Stochastic flow problem

In this work, the forward model \mathcal{F} is a system of partial differential equations (PDEs) that describes single-phase fluid flow in a porous medium. Let $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be the domain, with boundary Γ and unit outward normal \mathbf{n} , occupied by a heterogeneous and rigid porous medium saturated by water. The single-phase flow of an incompressible fluid, in the absence of gravity, is governed by the equations:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v}_D(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{v}_D(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\bar{\bar{\kappa}}(\mathbf{x})}{\mu} \nabla p(\mathbf{x}), \quad (3)$$

where \vec{v}_D is the Darcy velocity, \mathbf{q} is the source term, p and μ are the pressure and viscosity of the fluid, respectively. We consider a homogeneous porosity field ($\phi = 0.2$). Under the assumption of isotropy, the permeability tensor $\bar{\bar{\kappa}}$ is treated as a scalar (κ). Here, $\mathcal{D} = [0, 100] \times [0, 100] \text{m}^2$ is a square two-dimensional domain discretized in a regular mesh of 50×50 elements (Figure 1). Permeability is piecewise constant within each element.

We consider a five-spot well arrangement with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions (Figure 1). A Peaceman-type model is used to represent the wells. A flow rate ($\mathbf{q} = 100 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$) is imposed on the injection well,

and a constant bottom hole pressure ($p_{bh} = 1.01325 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$) on the production wells. The water viscosity is equal $10^{-3} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$. A standard centered finite-difference scheme (two-point flux, TPFA) was used to approximate the solution of the mathematical problem given by Eq. (3) (Lie, 2019).

Figure 1: Domain \mathcal{D} . The injection well is indicated in red at the center of the domain, while the production wells are marked in blue. Black crosses represent pressure sensors.

2.2. Permeability modeling

The permeability field, $\kappa(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$, is treated as a random space function with statistics inferred from geostatistical models. Here $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and ω is a random element in the probability space. In line with Dagan (1989) and Gelhar (1993), the permeability field is modeled as a log-normally distributed function

$$\kappa(\mathbf{x}, \omega) = \varrho \exp\left[\rho \mathbf{Y}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)\right], \quad (4)$$

where $\varrho, \rho \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $\mathbf{Y}(\mathbf{x}, \omega) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{\mathbf{Y}}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{Y}})$ is a Gaussian random field characterized by its mean $\mu_{\mathbf{Y}} = \langle \mathbf{Y} \rangle$ and two-point covariance function $\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$. Here, we consider a squared exponential covariance function

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sigma_{\mathbf{Y}}^2 \exp\left(-\frac{|x_1 - y_1|^2}{2\ell_1^2} - \frac{|x_2 - y_2|^2}{2\ell_2^2}\right), \quad (5)$$

with $\sigma_{\mathbf{Y}}^2$ denoting the variance and $\ell_i > 0$ ($i = 1, 2$) the correlation lengths. In our studies, we set $\varrho = 9.87 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$, $\rho = 1.0$, $\sigma_{\mathbf{Y}}^2 = 1.0$, and for sim-

plicity, $\ell_1 = \ell_2 = \ell = 20.0\text{m}$. By definition, $\mathbb{C}_Y(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is bounded, symmetric, and positive definite.

2.2.1. Permeability parameterization

The flow problem (Eq. (3)) is approximated in a 50×50 mesh grid, and κ is constant per element; then, the stochastic dimension associated with the κ parameter is $\mathbf{d}_\kappa = 2,500$. In this work, we parameterize the correlated fields $Y(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$ (or equivalently, κ) from Eq. (4) using the Karhunen-Loève expansion (KLE) (Karhunen, 1946; Loève, 1955) to reduce the stochastic dimension. The KLE has been widely used to represent the permeability field in uncertainty quantification problems in porous media flows (Efendiev et al., 2005, 2006; Das et al., 2010; Mondal et al., 2010; Ginting et al., 2011, 2012). It is based on the eigen-decomposition of the covariance function, and the essential elements are summarized below.

The process Y can be expressed as

$$Y(\mathbf{x}, \omega) = \langle Y(\mathbf{x}) \rangle + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sqrt{\lambda_i} \Phi_i(\mathbf{x}) \theta_i(\omega), \quad (6)$$

where λ_i and Φ_i are the eigenvalues and the square-integrable orthogonal eigenfunctions of the covariance function $\mathbb{C}_Y(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$, respectively; $\theta_i(\omega)$ is a set of independent random variables. The eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of Eq. (6) are the solution of the homogeneous Fredholm integral equation of the second kind given by

$$\int_{\mathcal{D}} \mathbb{C}_Y(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \Phi(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = \lambda \Phi(\mathbf{y}). \quad (7)$$

By arranging the eigenvalues in descending order, the m truncated series is given by

$$Y(\mathbf{x}, \omega) \approx \langle Y(\mathbf{x}) \rangle + \sum_{i=1}^m \sqrt{\lambda_i} \Phi_i(\mathbf{x}) \theta_i(\omega). \quad (8)$$

The number of terms in the expansion is determined by the partial energy carried by a subset of the eigenvalues, as defined by the following expression:

$$E(m) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_j}, \quad (9)$$

Thus, if the eigenvalues decay fast, we can truncate the expansion to a small number of terms, significantly reducing the stochastic dimension of

the problem while retaining most of the energy of the process. Specifically, in this work, we will use 24 eigenpairs to maintain an energy greater than 98%. Therefore, we obtain a reduction of stochastic dimension from 2,500 to $d = 24$.

The KLE provides orthogonal deterministic basis functions and uncorrelated random coefficients, allowing for the optimal encapsulation of the information contained in the random process into a set of discrete uncorrelated random variables (Ghanem and Spanos, 1991). We use this feature to simplify the Bayesian problem: the search can now be performed in the space of discrete, uncorrelated random variables ($\boldsymbol{\theta} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{24}]^T$), rather than in the space of permeabilities ($\boldsymbol{\kappa}$), which has a more complex statistical structure. Then, the Eq. (2) can be rewritten as

$$\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \propto P(\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) P(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (10)$$

In the following section, we describe the Metropolis algorithm used to sample the *a posteriori* distribution of the parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

3. Markov Chain Monte Carlo Method (McMC)

Markov chain Monte Carlo (McMC) algorithms are among the most essential tools to sample from the posterior distribution $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ given by Eq. (10). The Metropolis McMC Algorithm (1) (MT), introduced by Metropolis et al. (1953), has been widely used across several scientific fields.

Algorithm 1 Metropolis McMC Algorithm (MT) (Metropolis et al., 1953)

- 1: **procedure** METROPOLIS(MaxIter) ▷ MaxIter: maximum number of iterations
- 2: **Initialization:** Generate the initial state $\boldsymbol{\theta}^1$ from *a priori* distribution
- 3: **for** $t = 1$ to MaxIter **do**
- 4: **Step 1.** At state $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t$ generate $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ from the proposal distribution $q(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})$
- 5: **Step 2.** Take the new state as

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}^{t+1} = \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\theta}, & \text{with probability } \alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ \boldsymbol{\theta}^t, & \text{with probability } 1 - \alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \end{cases},$$

where

$$\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \min\left\{1, \frac{\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)}\right\}. \quad (11)$$

- 6: **end for**
 - 7: **return** $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}^1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{\text{MaxIter}}\}$
 - 8: **end procedure**
-

In the Algorithm (1) $\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the instrumental proposal distribution and $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the acceptance probability.

Assuming that the error between the observed and simulated data (\mathbf{D}^{sim}) has a normal distribution, the likelihood in the Eq. (10) is approximated as

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \text{P}(\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) \propto \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\| \mathbf{D}^{\text{sim}} - \mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} \|}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (12)$$

Here, σ is the overall precision associated with measurement, numerical, and modeling errors. The numerator of the term within the exponential function, called the relative error, is approximated numerically by

$$\text{RE} = \| \mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}} - \mathbf{D}^{\text{sim}} \| = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\text{Nd}} [\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}}(\mathbf{x}_i) - \mathbf{D}^{\text{sim}}(\mathbf{x}_i)]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{\text{Nd}} [\mathbf{D}^{\text{obs}}(\mathbf{x}_i)]^2}}, \quad (13)$$

where Nd is the number of data in space (here, $\text{Nd} = 25$ sensors at Figure 1).

The Metropolis algorithm can be used when the *a priori* knowledge of the target distribution is quite limited. A proposed value $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is generated from some pre-established density function \mathbf{q} , which is then accepted with probability $\alpha(\cdot, \cdot)$ following Algorithm (1). The function \mathbf{q} is typically chosen from some distribution family (e.g., a normal distribution centered at $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t$). The shape and size of the proposal distribution $\mathbf{q}(\cdot)$ are crucial for the algorithm's performance and the convergence of the Markov chain (Gilks and Roberts, 1996; Haario et al., 1999; Roberts and Rosenthal, 2001). In this context, we present several classical choices for \mathbf{q} and propose a new one that yields a more efficient algorithm.

3.1. Classical proposal functions

In this section, we summarize well-established methodologies in the literature that provide the theoretical basis for our new method, which combines the strengths of two of them into a synergistic result.

3.1.1. Random-Walk McMC (RW)

The simplest proposal function $\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})$, so-called random walk Metropolis algorithm (RW), is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}^t + \beta \boldsymbol{\xi}^t. \quad (14)$$

Here β controls the jump between successive parameters and $\boldsymbol{\xi}^t \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$ is a Gaussian perturbation. The proposal step defined in Eq. (14) is symmetric. Following Roberts and Rosenthal (2001), the main weakness of the RW is that the acceptance rate decreases rapidly for increasing β , especially in high-dimensional problems.

3.1.2. Preconditioned Crank-Nicolson McMC (pCN)

The proposal strategy called pCN (preconditioned Crank–Nicolson), proposed by Cotter et al. (2013), had its theoretical foundation in the work of Hairer et al. (2007) in the context of functional spaces (infinite dimension), such as those that appear in Bayesian inverse problems in stochastic partial differential equations (Dashti and Stuart, 2017; Ou et al., 2024). This can also be seen as a particular case of a first-order auto-regressive model (Gamerman and Lopes, 2006; Almeida and Czado, 2012). The central idea is to propose new candidates in a Markov chain in such a way that the *a priori* measure is invariant under the proposal, that is, the acceptance/rejection depends only on the likelihood function (via Metropolis algorithm) to solve the problem of traditional proposals (such as random walk Metropolis - RW) degrading severely as the dimension increases. The pCN proposals are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = \left(\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}\right) \boldsymbol{\theta}^t + \beta \boldsymbol{\xi}^t, \quad (15)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}^t \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$ is a Gaussian random perturbation independent of the chain, $\beta \in (0, 1]$ is the tuning parameter associated with the jump and $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t$ is the current state of the chain. This reversible proposal preserves the prior distribution as invariant, ensuring that the Metropolis acceptance probability depends only on the likelihood. A simple way to show invariance is to assume that both $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\xi}^t \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$, then, from Eq. (15), we have that $\boldsymbol{\theta} \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$.

The pCN scheme has been used in several recent works in its classical form for porous media problems (Xu et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2021; Reuschen et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2024; Vanmechelen et al., 2025), and some modifications have been proposed. Despite the improvement achieved by pCN over the classical random walk Metropolis, in high dimensions, the choice of the jump (β in Eq. (15)) remains problematic. To overcome this drawback, Hu et al. (2017) developed an adaptive version of the pCN algorithm, where the covariance operator of the proposal distribution is adjusted based on sampling history. However, this depends on computing the covariance operator, which can be costly. The work of Xu et al. (2020) combined the pCN scheme with the Parallel Tempering technique to create the method called

pCN-PT. This method has proven to be more efficient than traditional McMC methods, and even than pCN-McMC alone, for inverse problems related to hydraulic conductivity in underground aquifers.

3.1.3. Differential Evolution McMC (DE)

To solve the problem of choosing the appropriate scale and orientation of the jumping distribution, ter Braak (2006) developed a population-based McMC algorithm to enhance the efficiency of McMC sampling, integrating Differential Evolution genetic algorithm ideas into the Metropolis algorithm, resulting in the Differential Evolution Markov chain Monte Carlo method (DE) that allows for the exchange of information among multiple chains running in parallel. Turner et al. (2013) demonstrate that DE is an efficient proposal generator, and its performance is unaffected by the correlation of the target distribution, whereas conventional random walk McMC performs substantially worse as the correlation increases.

Briefly, the method can be described as follows: Let Θ^t be a population of N_c chains at state t ($\Theta^t = (\theta_1^t, \dots, \theta_{N_c}^t) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^{N_c}$). Each member of the population is given by the d -dimensional parameter. Thus, Θ^t is a $N_c \times d$ matrix. For each iteration, samples are drawn based on:

$$\theta = \theta_a^t + \gamma (\theta_b^t - \theta_c^t) + \mathbf{e}^t, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{e}^t is drawn from a symmetric distribution with a small variance compared to that of the target, but with unbounded support, e.g., $\mathbf{e}^t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{b}\mathbf{I}_d)$ with \mathbf{b} small to ensure irreducibility (\mathbf{I}_d is the d -dimensional identity matrix). Here, θ_b^t and θ_c^t are randomly selected without replacement from the current population $\Theta^{t \setminus a}$ (the population without θ_a^t), i.e., $a \neq b \neq c \neq a$. The parameter $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the scale factor. The chains are initialized from overdispersed states and, in parallel, learn from one another during the process.

For large N_c and small \mathbf{b} , the proposal (16) thus looks like $\theta = \theta^t + \gamma \varepsilon$ with $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon] = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbb{C}_\varepsilon = 2\mathbf{\Sigma}$, the covariance matrix of the target. In particular, if $\pi(\cdot)$ is multivariate normal, then $\gamma \varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, 2\gamma^2 \mathbf{\Sigma})$ so that DE is expected to behave like RW, but with correct scale and direction.

The method was used in several works (ter Braak and Vrugt, 2008; Vrugt et al., 2009; Turner et al., 2013; Vrugt, 2016; Sherri et al., 2019). ter Braak and Vrugt (2008) proposed an extension of DE to deal with high dimensions using a few parallel chains by exploiting past states. Vrugt et al. (2009) proposed the Differential Evolution Adaptive Metropolis or DREAM method, which uses DE as its main building block. In DREAM more than one pair of

states may be used to generate the proposal. DREAM variants can be found at Vrugt and Ter Braak (2011); Laloy and Vrugt (2012); Sadegh and Vrugt (2014) and others.

The major challenge of DE is related to the number of chains required for the method to work properly. The difference term $(\theta_b^t - \theta_c^t)$, in Eq. (16), works as a stochastic estimator of the target distribution’s covariance matrix. Therefore, using a large number of chains is essential for accurately estimating the jump scale and orientation, and for the method to be efficient. With few chains, this estimate of scale and orientation is poor or incomplete, resulting in limited coverage of the parameter space. That is, if $N_c \leq d$ (the stochastic dimension of the problem), all jumps are confined to a hyperplane, and exploration relies exclusively on the small noise \mathbf{e} , resulting in slow convergence. ter Braak (2006) recommends populations (number of chains) $N_c \approx 2$ to 3 times the dimension d for uni-modal targets and $N_c \geq 10d$ for multi-modal distributions, which may make its application to high-dimensional problems unfeasible. Next, we shall present a new population-based method that relaxes this restriction.

4. Preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution Markov Chain Method (pCNDE)

The central idea of this work is to combine the pCN and DE proposal strategies to develop a new approach that leverages the strengths of both. Inspired by the DE method, we introduce a new difference term into a population-based pCN method that exchanges information between parallel chains, yielding estimates of the scale and orientation of the jumping distribution. The proposal of the new preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution Markov chain Monte Carlo method (pCNDE), for a given component a ($a \in [1, \dots, N_c]$), is given by

$$\theta_a = \sqrt{1 - (2\gamma^2 + \delta^2)}\theta_a^t + \gamma(\theta_b^t - \theta_c^t) + \delta\xi^t, \quad (17)$$

where ξ^t is drawn from a symmetric distribution, e.g., $\xi^t \sim \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$. For the Eq. (17) to be consistent, $\gamma \in [0, \sqrt{1/2})$ and $0 < \delta < \sqrt{1 - 2\gamma^2}$. Figure 2 shows the relation between the parameters γ , β and δ . The choice of θ_b^t and θ_c^t follows the same scheme of DE method.

The DE and the RW methods suffer from the same degradation in acceptance rate as the stochastic dimension increases. This problem is solved because the new scheme is invariant under the proposals. Prior invariance is a property of the proposal kernel and does not require the ensemble to be

Figure 2: Relation between γ and δ . The dashed line refers to the δ_{\max} case. Given a value of $\gamma \in [0, \sqrt{1/2}]$, δ can assume values in the shaded area of the graph ($0 < \delta < \sqrt{1 - 2\gamma^2}$).

distributed according to the prior throughout the sampling procedure. Posterior invariance follows from the Metropolis–Hastings correction under the usual detailed-balance (reversibility) condition. Consequently, the ensemble coupling introduced through differential directions preserves the function-space well-posedness of the underlying pCN framework. In addition, the last term in Eq. (17) serves as a random-walk component, allowing fewer chains to be used by improving parameter-space exploration. In genetic algorithms, this term serves as a source of mutation, increasing variability even with fewer chains. Therefore, a balance between γ and δ enables the method to work closer to DE or pCN. Note that, taking $\gamma = 0$ and $\delta = \beta$ in Eq. (17), the pCN method is recovered (Eq. (15)).

The pCNDE proposal inherits structural properties from both the pCN and DE schemes, but is not identical to either. Nevertheless, the resulting Markov chain satisfies the standard conditions ensuring the existence and uniqueness of the stationary distribution.

In particular, since $\delta > 0$, the proposal kernel contains a non-degenerate Gaussian component with full support in \mathbb{R}^d , ensuring irreducibility and aperiodicity of the chain. Combined with the detailed balance property established in Section 4.1, this implies that the posterior distribution π is invariant and is the unique stationary distribution of the Markov chain. Thus, although the proposal differs from classical pCN and DE the convergence guarantees follow from standard Metropolis–Hastings theory under

the same regularity conditions on the likelihood function. Provided that the likelihood function is strictly positive on sets of positive Lebesgue measure, irreducibility follows from the full-support Gaussian proposal.

4.1. pCNDE Method Analysis

Let the prior measure $\mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$ be the standard Gaussian and the posterior distribution be $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \propto \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$. To verify prior invariance of the proposal kernel, we consider the auxiliary setting in which the ensemble Θ^t is distributed according to the product prior measure

$$\prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i).$$

This assumption is used solely for analytical purposes and does not restrict the actual evolution of the Markov chain. Under this assumption, the components $\boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t$ are independent $\mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$ random vectors. The innovation term $\boldsymbol{\xi}^t \sim \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$ is independent of the ensemble. This assumption is used solely to verify that the proposal preserves the prior measure; posterior invariance is subsequently enforced through the Metropolis–Hastings correction.

Fix an index $a \in \{1, \dots, N_c\}$. Let $b, c \in \{1, \dots, N_c\} \setminus \{a\}$ be distinct, chosen uniformly at random, without replacement. Since the indices are selected symmetrically, this mechanism preserves the exchangeability required for detailed balance.

Conditionally on the current ensemble $\Theta^t = (\boldsymbol{\theta}_1^t, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{N_c}^t) \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^{N_c}$, the pCNDE proposal for component a is

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_a = \sqrt{1 - (2\gamma^2 + \delta^2)} \boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t + \gamma (\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t - \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t) + \delta \boldsymbol{\xi}^t. \quad (18)$$

The proposed ensemble is $\Theta = (\boldsymbol{\theta}_1^t, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{a-1}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_a, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{a+1}^t, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{N_c}^t)$, i.e. only component a is updated. Then, $q(\boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_a | \Theta^t)$ denotes the conditional proposal density of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_a$ given the current ensemble Θ^t .

Now consider the pair:

$$\mathbf{X} := \boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{Y} := \nu \boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t + \gamma (\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t - \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t) + \delta \boldsymbol{\xi}^t,$$

where $\nu = \sqrt{1 - (2\gamma^2 + \delta^2)}$.

Proposition 1. *The pair (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) is jointly Gaussian with mean-zero and covariance:*

$$\mathbb{V}[\mathbf{X}] = \mathbf{I}_d, \quad \mathbb{V}[\mathbf{Y}] = \mathbf{I}_d, \quad \mathbb{C}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = \nu \mathbf{I}_d.$$

Here $\mathbb{V}[\cdot]$ designates the variance operator.

Proof. Since $\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t, \boldsymbol{\xi}^t$ are independent mean-zero Gaussian, \mathbf{Y} is a linear combination of Gaussian vectors, hence Gaussian and mean-zero. By the definition of prior, $\mathbb{V}[\mathbf{X}] = \mathbf{I}_d$. For \mathbf{Y} , we compute

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{V}[\mathbf{Y}] &= \mathbb{V}[\nu\mathbf{X} + \gamma(\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t - \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t) + \delta\boldsymbol{\xi}^t] \\ &= \nu^2\mathbb{V}[\mathbf{X}] + \gamma^2(\mathbb{V}[\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t] + \mathbb{V}[\boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t]) + \delta^2\mathbb{V}[\boldsymbol{\xi}^t], \\ &= \nu^2\mathbf{I}_d + 2\gamma^2\mathbf{I}_d + \delta^2\mathbf{I}_d = \mathbf{I}_d\end{aligned}$$

where $\nu^2 = [1 - (2\gamma^2 + \delta^2)]$ and since $\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t$ are independent $\mathbb{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}_d)$, we have $(\mathbb{V}[\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t] + \mathbb{V}[\boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t]) = 2\mathbf{I}_d$. For the cross-covariance, independence of $\mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t, \boldsymbol{\xi}^t$ gives

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{C}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) &= \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{X}\mathbf{Y}^\top] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\mathbf{X}[\nu\mathbf{X} + \gamma(\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t - \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t) + \delta\boldsymbol{\xi}^t]^\top\right] \\ &= \nu\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^\top] = \nu\mathbf{I}_d.\end{aligned}$$

This proves the claim. Thus, (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) is centered Gaussian vector with covariance

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_d & \nu\mathbf{I}_d \\ \nu\mathbf{I}_d & \mathbf{I}_d \end{pmatrix}.$$

□

Proposition 2. *The pair $(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = (\boldsymbol{\theta}_a^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}_a)$ has the same distribution as (\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) ; i.e., it is exchangeable.*

Proof. A centered Gaussian vector is fully characterized by its covariance. The covariance of (\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) is

$$\tilde{\Sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{V}[\mathbf{Y}] & \mathbb{C}(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) \\ \mathbb{C}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) & \mathbb{V}[\mathbf{X}] \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_d & \nu\mathbf{I}_d \\ \nu\mathbf{I}_d & \mathbf{I}_d \end{pmatrix} = \Sigma.$$

(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}) and (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) are centered Gaussian with the same covariance matrix, so they have the same distribution. □

This exchangeability implies that the proposal kernel satisfies detailed balance with respect to the prior distribution.

Let $m(x, y)$ denote the joint density of (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) , and let $\mathbf{q}(x, y)$ be the conditional density of \mathbf{Y} given $\mathbf{X} = x$;

$$m(x, y) = \mathbf{P}(x) \mathbf{q}(x, y).$$

By exchangeability, $m(x, y) = m(y, x)$ for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Therefore,

$$\mathbf{P}(x) \mathbf{q}(x, y) = \mathbf{P}(y) \mathbf{q}(y, x), \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}^d. \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) establishes the detailed balance of the proposal kernel with respect to the prior.

In a single-chain notation, given the current state $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t$ we generate a proposal $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ using the pCNDE kernel $\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \cdot)$ and accept it with probability

$$\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \min \left\{ 1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)} \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Thus the transition kernel \mathcal{K} of the chain is

$$\mathcal{K}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, d\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} + r(\boldsymbol{\theta})\delta_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(d\boldsymbol{\theta}),$$

where $r(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 1 - \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the probability of staying put.

Proposition 3. *Assume the prior detailed balance condition Eq. (19). Then the Metropolis-Hastings kernel \mathcal{K} with acceptance probability (20) is reversible with respect to the posterior $\pi(\cdot)$, i.e.,*

$$\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathcal{K}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, d\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathcal{K}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, d\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)$$

for all $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. In particular, π is invariant, and the chain is π -stationary.

Proof. Write $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t) = Z^{-1}\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)$ with normalizing constant $Z > 0$. For $\boldsymbol{\theta}^t \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}$ and using (19) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) &= Z^{-1}\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta})\min\left\{1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)}\right\} \\ &= Z^{-1}\min\{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\}\mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \\ &= Z^{-1}\min\{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\}\mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^t) \\ &= \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\min\left\{1, \frac{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^t)}{\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}\right\} \\ &= \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^t)\alpha(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^t). \end{aligned}$$

This establishes detailed balance for all $\boldsymbol{\theta} \neq \boldsymbol{\theta}^t$, and the diagonal term follows by normalization. \square

Remark 1. *For the ensemble $\boldsymbol{\Theta}^t = (\boldsymbol{\theta}_1^t, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{N_c}^t)$, the joint target density is the product measure*

$$\Pi(\boldsymbol{\Theta}^t) \propto \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i) \mathbf{P}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i).$$

The pCNDE algorithm updates a single component θ_a at a time using the proposal (18) and the acceptance probability (20), while keeping all other components fixed. Since each component-wise update satisfies detailed balance with respect to its marginal posterior, and updates are performed sequentially, the resulting Markov kernel is reversible with respect to the product measure. Therefore, by a standard Metropolis-within-Gibbs argument, the full-ensemble transition kernel preserves the product measure II.

Finally, we note that the pCNDE proposal preserves the Gaussian prior structure despite incorporating differential evolution directions. This follows from the fact that the proposal remains a linear combination of independent Gaussian variables with carefully balanced coefficients, ensuring that both marginal variances and cross-covariances satisfy the requirements for reversibility. Consequently, the Metropolis-Hastings correction depends only on the likelihood, retaining the dimension-robust properties of pCN while benefiting from adaptive, ensemble-based proposal directions.

4.2. MCMC method efficiency

Although convergence diagnostics ensure that a Markov chain targets the correct posterior distribution, the practical performance of a sampling algorithm depends on how efficiently it reaches and explores the stationary regime. Efficiency is often summarized by the effective sample size (ESS), defined in terms of the integrated autocorrelation time (Vats et al., 2019). However, the analysis of Seiffert and Pereira (2024) suggests that in strongly correlated PDE inverse problems, the empirical ESS estimator may fail to stabilize asymptotically as the number of samples increases, even when multichain diagnostics indicate convergence. For this reason, we prioritize multichain stabilization diagnostics, posterior consistency checks, and wall-clock normalized efficiency measures rather than relying on ESS. In this work, efficiency is assessed using the diagnostics introduced in Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2.

4.2.1. Convergence analysis

Under a few conditions, the Metropolis algorithm converges to the target distribution as the number of draws approaches infinity. However, there are rarely strong guarantees about its behavior after a finite time (Vehtari et al., 2021). In this work, the convergence of multiple Markov chains, initialized from a diverse set of starting points, will be assessed using the multivariate potential scale reduction factor (MPSRF) proposed by Gelman and Rubin (1992); Brooks and Gelman (1998). Essentially, MPSRF monitors within- and between-chain variance and is thus a method based on moments (see

Gelman and Rubin (1992); Brooks and Gelman (1998); Brooks et al. (2003); Gelman et al. (2013); Vehtari et al. (2021) for more details). We declare convergence when $\widehat{R} < 1.2$ (Gelman and Rubin, 1992).

4.2.2. Acceptance rate (AR)

By Roberts and Rosenthal (2001), the algorithm’s efficiency is related to its acceptance rate, defined as the probability (in stationarity) that the chain’s proposed move is accepted. In this work, the acceptance rate of each chain i ($i = 1, \dots, N_c$) is approximated as follows:

$$AR_i = \frac{NA_i}{NT} \times 100, \quad (21)$$

where NA is the number of accepted moves in NT iterations for each chain after eliminating the burn-in period. Given that the chains’ convergence has been diagnosed, the mean acceptance rate, defined as:

$$\widehat{AR} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} AR_i, \quad (22)$$

can be used to evaluate the efficiency of the proposed methods.

4.3. Asynchronous DE-like methods

DE-like methods, which exchange information between chains, are traditionally implemented in parallel, with all chains progressing together; that is, at the end of each iteration, the processes must exchange messages synchronously. This approach incurs communication overhead, and the slowest processor limits chain advancement, potentially compromising the method’s efficiency. To overcome these issues, we consider an asynchronous parallel version of the algorithm in which the exchanged information is updated at specific intervals (every N_{up} iterations) rather than at every iteration, as in the synchronous scheme.

Asynchronous implementations of population-based MCMC methods allow chains to evolve independently over computational time, reducing synchronization overhead while preserving ergodicity and invariance of the target distribution under mild conditions (Craiu et al., 2009). Vrugt et al. (2009) verifies that asynchronous schemes may improve scalability and sampling efficiency in computationally intensive problems by mitigating synchronization costs without compromising convergence to the target distribution.

Each process contains a local matrix ($\Theta_{[N_c, d]}^t$) that stores the states of all processes, which are used to exchange information. A broadcast operation

periodically updates this matrix. In practice, the process rank-zero controls when updates should occur, sending a signal to the other processes.

The asynchronous implementation induces a time-inhomogeneous Markov chain, since the proposal at a given iteration may depend on ensemble states computed at different computational times. However, at each iteration, the Metropolis–Hastings acceptance probability is computed using the correct posterior density π , and the proposal contains a non-degenerate Gaussian innovation term ($\delta > 0$). Therefore, every transition kernel in the sequence admits π as an invariant distribution. Provided that communication delays are uniformly bounded and ensemble states are refreshed infinitely often, the chain remains irreducible and aperiodic. Standard results for adaptive and parallel MCMC schemes (e.g., Craiu et al. (2009); Roberts and Rosenthal (2007); Rosenthal (2011)) then ensure that the invariant distribution is preserved and that the scheme is ergodic.

5. Numerical Results

In this section, we use the previously defined stochastic inversion problem (Section 2.1) to assess the proposed methodology. A synthetic study was conducted in which a Gaussian field, \mathbf{Y}^{ref} , was randomly generated to obtain the “true” permeability field using Eq. (4) at Section 2.2. Numerical simulation was then used to generate pressure data from the 25 sensors (\mathbf{D}^{obs}). The \mathbf{Y}^{ref} field and the corresponding pressure field are presented in the Figure 3.

The results obtained with the classic pCN method serve as a benchmark for evaluating the new proposal. In this case, the jump parameter was set to $\beta = 3.25 \times 10^{-2}$ (Eq. (15)). A precision of $\sigma = 3.5 \times 10^{-3}$ was considered in all cases (Eq. (12)). Again, it is important to note that the pCN can be viewed as a particular instance of the new methodology where $\gamma = 0.0$ and $\delta = 3.25 \times 10^{-2}$ in Eq. (17).

To perform a fair comparison between the pCN and pCNDE methods, in our experiments, we guarantee the same jump size for all experiments by doing $2\gamma^2 + \delta^2 = \beta^2$, which implies the following condition (see Figure 4):

$$\delta = \sqrt{\beta^2 - 2\gamma^2}, \quad \text{with the restriction that } \gamma \leq \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}\beta. \quad (23)$$

In line with this restriction, we explore three different combinations of γ and δ values so that the terms of Eq. (17) originating from the DE ($\gamma(\boldsymbol{\theta}_b^t - \boldsymbol{\theta}_c^t)$) and pCN ($\delta\xi^t$) methods are responsible for a specific percentage of the jump

(a) Gaussian field ($Y^{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{x})$)

(b) Pressure field ($p^{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{x})$)

Figure 3: Reference fields used to generate the synthetic data. The crosses represent pressure sensors.

(relative weight of each method). Thus, defining $\varphi_{\text{DE}} \in [0, 1)$ as the relative jump weight of the DE term, for a given β , we have

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\varphi_{\text{DE}} \frac{\beta^2}{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = \sqrt{(1 - \varphi_{\text{DE}}) \beta^2}. \quad (24)$$

Figure 4: Relation between the parameters of pCN and pCNDE.

Table 1 shows the values of γ and δ , considering $\beta = 3.25 \times 10^{-2}$ (used in the pCN experiments), for three different relative weights. Thus, in the first case, the scheme behaves closely to the pCN method, and in the third, closely to the DE. In the intermediate case (second), both methods have equal weights.

Parameter	Relative jump weight of the DE term (φ_{DE})		
	25%	50%	75%
δ	2.81×10^{-2}	2.30×10^{-2}	1.63×10^{-2}
γ	1.15×10^{-2}	1.63×10^{-2}	1.99×10^{-2}

Table 1: Parameter combination for pCNDE method, considering $\beta = 3.25 \times 10^{-2}$.

In our studies, we consider three main aspects: *i*) the relative jump weight of the DE term (φ_{DE}); *ii*) the effect of the number of parallel chains (N_{c}) used, and *iii*) the frequency of ensemble Θ updates (N_{up}), in accordance with Section 4.3. Therefore, to facilitate the identification of the pCNDE experiments, we consider the following notation: $\text{pCNDE}_{[\text{N}_{\text{c}}][\text{P}_{\text{N}_{\text{c}}}]^{[\varphi_{\text{DE}}][\text{N}_{\text{up}}]}}$. Here, $\text{P}_{\text{N}_{\text{c}}} \leq N_{\text{c}}$ is the number of randomly selected chains used in the post-processing of the results (important to make a fair comparison between experiments performed with different numbers of chains). For example, $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][24]}^{[25][50]}$ means that the experiment was performed with 48 parallel chains and with an $\varphi_{\text{DE}} = 25\%$ (see Table 1); the ensemble Θ was updated at each 50 iterations, and 24 chains (randomly chosen) were used in the post-processing.

To compare the methods, we use:

1. The number of iterations required to reach convergence (I_{R}), in accordance with Section 4.2.1;
2. The mean acceptance rate, AR , measured after convergence detection (see Section (4.2.2));
3. Mean CPU-time spent to compute one iteration, given in seconds (Ti).

CPU time is essential for assessing the computational efficiency of the method. Unlike the pCN method, in which the chains are independent from each other, regular DE-like methods exchange information between the chains and, therefore, have their evolution synchronized, causing a delay compared

to the independent case. Hence, when computing the efficiency of the methods, the average time per iteration for each method must be taken into account.

5.1. Benchmark results obtained using the pCN proposal.

We begin by presenting the results of the $\text{pCN}_{[48][48]}$ (or, equivalently, $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[00][\cdot]}$) method, which, as mentioned earlier, will be used for comparison with the new methodology. The reason for selecting 48 independent chains is explained in the next section. All experiments were performed on the SDumont supercomputer (<http://sdumont.lncc.br>). Each experiment was repeated 5 times, and the reported values are the ensemble means and standard deviations. Although each experiment was repeated 5 times, only one is shown (Figure 5) because the results were quite similar. The Figure 5(a) shows the rapid decay of the relative error (Eq. (13)) and its subsequent stabilization across the 48 chains. The acceptance rate, calculated in batches of $\text{NT} = 7,500$ iterations (Eq. (21)), remained almost constant around its average value (7.5%), a desirable behavior (Figure 5(b)). The Figure 5(c) shows the monotonic decay of the MPSRF (or \hat{R}), reaching the convergence criterion adopted after 160,297 iterations. Finally, the mean and error (\pm standard deviation) of the pressure in the sensors, obtained after simulating 2,000 realizations of the permeability fields belonging to the posterior distribution (chosen randomly), are presented in the Figure 5(d). There is good agreement between the reference data and the simulations, showing that the method performed very well.

Figure 6 provides a visual inspection of the Gaussian fields in the posterior distribution. Figure 6(a) shows 4 realizations (chosen randomly), while Figure 6(b) shows the mean and standard deviation of a set of 2,000 realizations. The mean field and the 4 realizations show similarities to the reference field (Figure 3(a)). Because numerous experiments yielded similar results that provide no new information, the remaining figures will not be shown.

5.2. Effect of the number of parallel chains on the pCNDE method

We began evaluating the new method by examining how the ensemble population size affected the results. The main drawback of DE-like methods is their population-based nature. Unlike single-chain MCMC algorithms, DE-like methods generate proposals using scaled differences between randomly selected chains from the population. Then, the performance of MCMC methods based on Differential Evolution depends strongly on the number of chains

Figure 5: Results for the method $\text{pCN}_{[48][48]}$. a) Relative error given by Eq. (13); b) acceptance rate given by Eq. (21); c) Multivariate potential scale reduction (MPSRF or \widehat{R}) and; d) data and posterior pressure at the sensors.

(a) Samples

(b) Mean (left) and standard deviation (right)

Figure 6: Gaussian fields Y . a) four realizations belonging to the posterior distribution; b) ensemble mean and standard deviation (2,000 realizations).

in the ensemble. In contrast to single-chain algorithms, the population of chains is an integral part of the proposal mechanism, as new candidate states are generated using scaled differences between states of distinct chains (ter Braak, 2006). As the number of chains increases, the population provides an increasingly accurate empirical approximation of the target distribution’s covariance structure. This improves the orientation and scaling of proposal directions, leading to enhanced mixing and more efficient exploration of the parameter space, particularly for high-dimensional, strongly correlated, or multimodal posterior distributions (ter Braak and Vrugt, 2008).

The number of chains also plays a critical role in convergence behavior. Larger ensembles promote greater diversity among differential vectors, reducing autocorrelation within individual chains and accelerating convergence toward the stationary distribution. Moreover, convergence diagnostics based on between-chain and within-chain variability, such as the MPSRF, become more reliable as the number of chains increases (Gelman and Rubin, 1992; Brooks and Gelman, 1998). In high-dimensional problems, using too few chains can lead to rank-deficient empirical covariance estimates, resulting in degenerate proposal directions and severely reduced sampling efficiency.

Acceptance rates and proposal scaling are likewise influenced by the ensemble size. Theoretical results for the optimal scaling of DE-like proposals assume a large and diverse population of chains, yielding the commonly adopted scaling factor proportional to $2.38/\sqrt{2d}$, where d denotes the parameter dimension (Gelman et al., 1996; ter Braak, 2006). When the number of chains is small, correlations among differential vectors increase, often reducing acceptance rates and inducing random-walk behavior. Increasing the ensemble size stabilizes acceptance probabilities and reduces sensitivity to tuning parameters.

In summary, the number of chains in DE-like methods represents a fundamental trade-off between statistical efficiency and computational cost. An ensemble size that is sufficiently large to capture the structure of the target distribution is essential for effective performance, particularly in high-dimensional settings. Hypothetically, the new method pCNDE is less dependent on the number of parallel chains due to the last term of Eq. (17).

In light of what has been presented so far in this section, an experiment was designed to evaluate the effect of the number of parallel chains on the new pCNDE method. All experiments were performed with $\varphi_{DE} = 75\%$ (greater weight given to the DE term), and $N_{up} = 1$ (synchronous), with 5 repetitions. We considered the following cases: 12, 24, 48, 120 and 240 chains (equivalent to $d/2, d, 2d, 5d, 10d$, where $d = 24$). For a fair comparison, all

results were post-processed using 12 chains (chosen randomly).

The results are summarized at Table 2. No significant differences were detected in any of the measures used in the comparison. This result indicates that the method maintained good performance even with a reduced population size ($d/2$).

Experiment	N_c	N_c/d	$l_{\hat{R}}$	$\sigma_{l_{\hat{R}}}$	AR	σ_{AR}
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][12]}^{[75][01]}$	240	10	111,432	8,754	23.70	0.06
$\text{pCNDE}_{[120][12]}^{[75][01]}$	120	5	97,172	3,979	23.71	0.19
$\text{pCNDE}_{[96][12]}^{[75][01]}$	96	4	110,156	13,238	23.79	0.05
$\text{pCNDE}_{[48][12]}^{[75][01]}$	48	2	107,495	12,123	23.84	0.14
$\text{pCNDE}_{[24][12]}^{[75][01]}$	24	1	110,780	9,391	23.89	0.09
$\text{pCNDE}_{[12][12]}^{[75][01]}$	12	1/2	107,372	7,7367	24.04	0.22

Table 2: Comparison of the pCNDE method performed with different numbers of chains. All calculations were performed using 12 randomly selected chains. No significant differences were found between the means using Tukey’s test at the 5% level.

The experiment $\text{pCNDE}_{[240][12]}^{[75][01]}$ was used to determine the number of chains employed in the other studies to obtain reliable estimates of $l_{\hat{R}}$ and AR. The Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation of the number of iterations required to achieve convergence and acceptance rate from 5 repetitions, using 12, 24, 48, 96, 120, and 240 parallel chains for computations. The results show that, as the number of chains increases, $l_{\hat{R}}$ initially decreases and stabilizes from 48 chains onward. The average acceptance rate was not statistically sensitive to the number of chains used in the calculation. Therefore, for the other studies, we will use $N_c = 48$. It is worth noting that this choice was made to ensure that the metrics used to compare the methods are well estimated.

Experiment	$\langle I_{\hat{R}} \rangle$	$\sigma_{I_{\hat{R}}}$	AR	σ_{AR}
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][12]}^{[75][01]}$	111,432 a	8,754	23.70 a	0.06
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][24]}^{[75][01]}$	108,875 a	15,248	23.67 a	0.06
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][48]}^{[75][01]}$	89,071 ab	15,304	23.71 a	0.08
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][96]}^{[75][01]}$	80,351 b	7,131	23.71 a	0.05
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][120]}^{[75][01]}$	82,759 b	12,411	23.71 a	0.05
$\text{pCNDE}_{[240][240]}^{[75][01]}$	78,924 b	6,223	23.70 a	0.06

Table 3: $\langle I_{\hat{R}} \rangle$ and **AR** computed with different numbers of chains. Means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level according to Tukey’s test.

5.3. Effect of relative jump weight of the DE term (φ_{DE}) on the efficiency of the pCNDE method

In this section, we study the effect of the relative weight of the term originating from the DE method parameterized by φ_{DE} . As described in Section (2.2), the stochastic dimension of our problem is $\mathbf{d} = 24$. Therefore, following the recommendation of ter Braak (2006) for DE-type methods, we ran the experiments with $N_c = 2\mathbf{d} = 48$ parallel chains to ensure the method worked. All chains were used for post-processing the data. Considering the aspects mentioned, in this analyses the following experiments were considered: $\text{pCN}_{[48][48]}$ (equivalent to $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[00][\cdot]}$), $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[25][01]}$, $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[50][01]}$, and $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[75][01]}$. Therefore, the experiments differ only in relation to the value of (φ_{DE}).

Figure 7 shows a significant and strong negative linear relationship between the mean number of iterations required to reach convergence ($\langle I_{\hat{R}} \rangle$) and the parameter φ_{DE} . The coefficient of determination shows that approximately 93.8% of the variability in ($\langle I_{\hat{R}} \rangle$) is explained by the linear model. Therefore, as φ_{DE} increases, the number of iterations required to reach convergence ($\langle I_{\hat{R}} \rangle$) decreases almost linearly. Using the model obtained (Figure 7), we can verify that experiment $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[75][01]}$ achieved convergence with only 38% of the iterations required by the standard scheme $\text{pCN}_{[48][48]}$ (or $\text{pCNDE}_{[48][48]}^{[00][\cdot]}$).

Figure 7: Linear regression of the mean response of the number of iterations required to reach convergence $\langle I_{\bar{R}} \rangle$ as a function of φ_{DE} . Blue circles represent the observed data, and the solid yellow line shows the fitted linear model. The superscript *** stands for statistical significance of the model with $p < 0.001$.

A strong nonlinear relationship between the parameter φ_{DE} and the mean acceptance rate $\langle AR \rangle$ is shown in Figure 8. The statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) indicates that the dependence of $\langle AR \rangle$ on φ_{DE} is highly unlikely to be due to random variation, and the coefficient of determination indicates that 99.7% of the variability in the observed acceptance rate is explained by the quadratic model. As φ_{DE} increases, the mean acceptance rate increases. For example, $\langle AR \rangle$ increased from 7.6% in the pCN method to 23.7% in the pCNDE method with $\varphi_{DE} = 75\%$, representing an increase of over 3.1 times, with practical implications for algorithm efficiency. From a MCMC perspective, once convergence has been achieved, the acceptance rate is an essential measure of the method's efficiency.

Figure 8: Linear regression of the mean response of acceptance rate ($\langle AR \rangle$) as a function of φ_{DE} . Blue circles represent the observed data, and the solid yellow line shows the fitted linear model. The superscript $***$ stands for statistical significance of the model with $p < 0.001$.

The average iteration time (T_i) for each scheme was measured independently on the same machine, with no memory limitations or competing processes, to ensure a fair comparison. Each scheme used 24 chains, and the reported times are the mean across these chains (see Table 4). The results show significant differences between the schemes. The pCN (asynchronous case) process is, on average, 1.68 times faster than the synchronous cases (pCNDE). This fact will be taken into account in the efficiency analysis of the new method presented in Section 4.2.

Experiment	Ti (<i>s/iteration</i>)
pCNDE $_{[48][48]}^{[75][01]}$	4.768×10^{-2} a
pCNDE $_{[48][48]}^{[25][01]}$	4.732×10^{-2} a
pCNDE $_{[48][48]}^{[50][01]}$	4.631×10^{-2} b
pCN $_{[48][48]}$	2.808×10^{-2} c

Table 4: Average iteration time of different schemes. Means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level according to Tukey’s test.

5.4. Effect of update frequency on the pCNDE method

As highlighted in Section (4.3), population-based DE methods exchange information across their parallel chains simultaneously, thereby incurring communication overhead and reducing computational efficiency. To mitigate this effect, an asynchronous version of the new method was implemented, in which the frequency of information updates exchanged between chains is user-defined. All experiments were performed with 48 chains and $\varphi_{DE} = 75\%$, with 5 repetitions. The following update frequencies were tested: $N_{up} = 1, 10, 50, 100$.

Table 5 presents the average results for each method. For $I_{\hat{R}}$ and AR, Tukey’s test does not identify significant differences between them at the 5% level. This result indicates that, at least for the tested values, the update frequency did not significantly affect the method’s performance. On the other hand, there was a significant decrease in computational time per iteration (Ti). Therefore, the asynchronous version of the method is essential for ensuring the efficiency of the new methodology. The times obtained for $N_{up} = 50$ and 100 are close from those obtained with the pCN method in which there is no information exchange ($Ti_{(pCN_{[48][48]})} = 2.80 \times 10^{-2}$).

Experiment	Average values		
	$l_{\hat{R}}$	AR (%)	Ti (<i>s/iteration</i>)
pCNDE _{[48][48]} ^{[75][01]}	71,746	23.85	4.768×10^{-2} a
pCNDE _{[48][48]} ^{[75][10]}	83,490	23.77	3.648×10^{-2} b
pCNDE _{[48][48]} ^{[75][50]}	73,177	23.92	2.879×10^{-2} c
pCNDE _{[48][48]} ^{[75][100]}	76,396	23.81	2.960×10^{-2} c

Table 5: Comparison of the pCNDE method performed with different update frequencies of the exchange information. Means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level according to Tukey’s test. No significant differences were found between the means of $l_{\hat{R}}$ and AR using Tukey’s test at the 5%.

5.5. Computational efficiency of pCNDE method

To assess the computational efficiency of the new method, we define a metric below that incorporates convergence, acceptance rate, and time per iteration. We start by defining the total time (in seconds) spent to yield Nm movements in the chain after convergence:

$$Tt_{(\text{met.})} = Ti_{(\text{met.})} (\langle l_{\hat{R}(\text{met.})} \rangle + Nr_{(\text{met.})}), \quad (25)$$

where ($Ti_{(\text{met.})}$ [*s/iteration*]) is the average time per iteration, and $Nr_{(\text{met.})}$ is the average number of iterations required for scheme *met.* to produce Nm distinct states (chain moves), given by:

$$Nr_{(\text{met.})} = \frac{Nm}{\langle AR_{(\text{met.})} \rangle}. \quad (26)$$

Finally, considering the pCN method as a reference, the relative efficiency of each scheme is given by:

$$Eff_{(\text{met.})} = \frac{Tt_{(\text{pCN}_{[48][48]})}}{Tt_{(\text{met.})}}. \quad (27)$$

Figure 9: Comparison between the MCMC methods. Means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level according to Tukey’s test.

The Figure 9 shows the relative efficiency of the evaluated methods. The synchronous versions of pCNDE methods with $\varphi_{DE} = 50$ and 25 exhibited efficiency equal to or less than pCN. The other versions offer superior efficiency. The highest efficiency values were obtained for the asynchronous versions of pCNDE with $N_{up} = 50$ and 100 (no statistically significant difference). Therefore, in these versions, we achieve an average efficiency of 2.89 times that of the classic pCN method.

6. Conclusions

In this work, we proposed the preconditioned Crank–Nicolson Differential Evolution (pCNDE) method, a population-based MCMC scheme designed for high-dimensional Bayesian inverse problems governed by partial differential equations. The method combines the prior-invariant structure of the pCN proposal with differential evolution directions derived from an ensemble of chains, allowing the algorithm to exploit population information while preserving the theoretical properties required for correct posterior sampling.

The resulting proposal maintains prior invariance and satisfies detailed balance through the Metropolis–Hastings correction, ensuring that the pos-

terior distribution remains invariant. At the same time, the differential evolution component introduces informed proposal directions that improve exploration of correlated posterior structures while retaining the dimension-robust behavior characteristic of pCN-based methods.

Numerical experiments demonstrate that incorporating differential evolution directions substantially improves sampling efficiency. In particular, the proposed method reduces the number of iterations required for convergence while increasing the acceptance rate compared with the classical pCN scheme. When evaluated using a combined efficiency metric that accounts for convergence iterations, acceptance rate, and computational cost, several pCNDE configurations outperform the standard pCN method, with the asynchronous implementation providing the best overall performance.

These results indicate that combining prior-preserving proposals with population-based directions provides an effective strategy to improve the efficiency of MCMC methods for computationally intensive inverse problems. Future work will investigate adaptive parameter selection, scalability to larger ensembles, and applications to more complex large-scale Bayesian inference problems.

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